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Community-Based Tourism and Development of Waterfall Attractions in Southwest, Nigeria: Case of Erin Ijesha and Arinta Waterfalls

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Abstract

This study examined community-based Tourism (CBT) and the development of waterfall attractions in Southwest Nigeria, focusing on Erin-Ijesha and Arinta waterfalls. Using a descriptive survey design, the research explored community roles in developing these attractions, particularly their participation levels, satisfaction, and perceived impact on host communities. A total of 365 residents participated in the survey; the data was collected through self-structured questionnaires measuring community roles, participation, satisfaction, and the impact of waterfall development. Descriptive (percentages and mean ranking) and inferential statistics (independent sample t-tests and ANOVA) were employed for analysis. The findings revealed that, while communities are seen as integral to waterfall project planning, government consultations, and tourism promotion, actual participation in these developmental activities is low, resulting in widespread dissatisfaction. However, despite the limited participation, residents perceive positive impacts of the waterfalls on cultural heritage and environmental sustainability. Additionally, demographic factors such as age and religious affiliation were found to influence participation levels and perceptions of tourism development. The study underscores the need for greater community involvement and satisfaction in waterfall development to foster sustainable tourism and preserve cultural and environmental resources in Southwest Nigeria.

Keywords: Community-Based Tourism, Waterfall Attraction, Community Development, Community Participation, Stakeholders

Introduction

Tourism, through appropriate promotion has the capacity to drive infrastructure development in destinations. To cater for the needs of tourists, governments and private entities invest in transportation networks, airports, roads, hotels, restaurants, and recreational facilities. These developments not only benefit tourists but also enhance the quality of life for local residents. Furthermore, the tourism industry provides employment opportunities for diverse groups of people, including those in rural areas and remote communities. It generates income for local businesses, artisans and service providers, contributing to the overall development and empowerment of communities. It can foster peace and understanding by promoting intercultural dialogue and breaking down stereotypes and prejudices. As people from different backgrounds interact, they develop a better understanding and appreciation of each other's perspectives, leading to greater tolerance and harmony (Folorunso *et al.*, 2017).

There are various types of tourism activities and events that cater for different interests and preferences of tourists. They include leisure tourism, cultural tourism, adventure tourism, ecotourism, culinary tourism, wellness tourism, sports tourism, volunteering tourism, business tourism and religious tourism among others. Waterfall attractions typically fall under the categories of nature or adventure tourism and ecotourism. Waterfalls are often considered natural wonders and attract tourists who appreciate the beauty and serenity of natural landscapes. Nature tourism focuses on experiencing and appreciating the natural environment (Asada & Yong, 2019). Visitors may engage in activities such as hiking, sightseeing, photography and picnicking while enjoying the scenic beauty of waterfalls.

Adebayo and Jim (2023) note that the shamble state of the Nigerian waterfall attractions and their low contribution to the overall Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of the nation attest to the fact that tourism stakeholders are not playing substantial roles as expected in the development of waterfalls in Nigeria. The Erin-Ijesha and Arinta waterfalls, for example, which are the focus of this study, have been attributed with a very low level of development and participation of the community. This implies that the waterfall attractions such as Erin-Ijesha and Arinta waterfalls, are below the international standard as they have failed in providing thrilling and fascinating experiences for visitors due to the lack of facilities and infrastructures, low funding and publicity, high level of illiteracy among the people and the lack of laws enforcement in the sector (Ajayi, 2017).

The attractions are less able to provide substantial job opportunities for the local residents, support local businesses fully enough, bring about initiatives that promote cultural preservation and heritage, as well as, promote and market the attraction through various channels such as online platforms, travel agencies, tourism events and collaborations with tour operators. This may be partly due to lack or low participation level of the community in the development and management of the waterfall. It is challenging to gain community participation in the African tourism development (Alikor, 2022).

Empirical studies are also lacking in this respect. Some of the available related studies assessed the tourism potentials of Gurara waterfalls, Niger State; it explored fishery and the tourism potential of Agbokum waterfalls. Another study investigated the tourism potentials of two waterfalls (Olumirin and Arinta) in Southwest Nigeria. The research focused on Olumirin waterfall tourist centre and socio-cultural transformation of Erin-Ijesa rural community. Another study examined the effect of warm spring in Ikogosi and Arinta waterfalls. An author investigated the attitudes of local residents towards sustainable ecotourism development in Olumirin waterfall while another expert examined the role of stakeholders in tourism sustainability in Kwame Nkrumah Mausoleum and centre for art and culture in Ghana (Ajayi, 2017).

Some studies from the above were conducted at Olumirin or Erin-Ijesha and Arinta waterfalls but they were silent on the community participation. Others were carried out outside these attractions but did not consider the role of the community. The relevant study was conducted in Ghana and not on waterfall tourism (Faladi-Obalade and Suchi, 2014). The research gaps indicated that there is paucity of empirical studies regarding the community participation in tourism development, particularly, waterfall attractions. Hence, this current study deems it imperative to investigate the community-based tourism and the development of waterfall attractions in Southwest Nigeria (Case of Erin-Ijesha and Arinta waterfalls in Osun State).

The aim of the study is to investigate community-based tourism and development of waterfall attractions, Erin-Ijesha and Arinta waterfalls, in Southwest Nigeria; and to investigate the role of community in the development of waterfall attractions in Southwest Nigeria. Research objectives guiding this study are: to determine the roles of the community in the development of waterfall attractions in Southwest, Nigeria; and to ascertain the level of community participation in the development of waterfall attractions.

Community-based Tourism

Community-based tourism (CBT) serves as a valuable instrument for community development by enhancing the capacity of rural communities to manage tourism resources and fostering active involvement from the local populace. The implementation of CBT can yield various benefits for the local community, such as income generation, economic diversification, cultural preservation, environmental conservation and educational opportunities. By offering alternative sources of income, CBT effectively functions as a means of alleviating poverty within these communities. It is imperative for CBT initiatives to adopt a comprehensive and sustained approach that prioritises maximising positive outcomes for the local community while mitigating adverse impacts of tourism on both the community and its environmental assets (Hoang, 2021).

Approaching community-based tourism in a methodical manner involves assessing the community's suitability for tourism engagement, facilitating active participation of community members in relevant initiatives and establishing mechanisms for monitoring and mitigating negative repercussions (Ajulo, *et*

al., 2017). Noteworthy characteristics of CBT, as outlined by UNEP and UNWTO, include fostering an appreciation for not only the natural environment but also the indigenous cultures present in these areas; integrating education and interpretation into the tourist experience; typically catering for small groups through small, specialised, and locally owned enterprises; minimising detrimental effects on the natural and socio-cultural surroundings; contributing to the safeguarding of natural and cultural sites through economic incentives; offering alternate sources of income and employment for local residents; and enhancing the awareness of both the locals and visitor regarding conservation efforts.

Community-based tourism (CBT) provides a distinctive opportunity for travellers to gain authentic insights into local cultures while simultaneously contributing positively to the welfare of indigenous communities. The nature of CBT encounters is diverse and contingent upon the specific country and the requirements of the local populace, thereby offering a bespoke and unparalleled travel experience. A unifying characteristic of these encounters is their complete ownership and administration by the community, ensuring that the benefits of visitors' stay extend beyond individual households to enrich the community collectively (Babafemi *et al.*, 2021).

According to Ijeomah and Alao (2007), community-based tourism (CBT) initiatives undergo a distinct product life-cycle characterised by a progression from small-scale, low-density operations managed by the local community with support from external entities such as NGOs. Initially, communities find satisfaction in the employment opportunities facilitated by these CBT projects. However, as the CBT projects evolve, the complexities and challenges faced by the community intensify. Consequently, tour operators inevitably express interest and seek to establish partnerships with the local community. In the absence of the requisite skills and knowledge to manage the growing influx of tourists and evolving travellers' preferences, local communities may become excessively dependent on tour operators. Concurrently, CBT projects must ascend the value chain and their sustained success hinges on the ability of key stakeholders to adapt to new demands and expectations effectively (Hoang, 2021).

Community-based tourism (CBT) exhibits noticeable similarities with broader community development and participatory planning ideologies, both of which advocate for increased community agency in local-level processes. Community development can be described as the establishment of vibrant and enduring communities founded on principles of social equity and mutual regard. Consequently, community development endeavours to dismantle systemic obstacles to participation and foster empowering collective responses to local challenges. However, Alikor (2022) stresses that proponents of CBT diverge from the principles of community development in several key aspects. Firstly, CBT narratives lack the transformative focus intrinsic to community development, positioning CBT primarily as a strategy for ensuring the enduring profitability of the tourism sector rather than a vehicle for empowering local inhabitants. Secondly, local communities are often portrayed as homogeneous entities, overlooking internal power dynamics and conflicting values within these communities. Thirdly, CBT narratives tend to disregard external factors that impede local autonomy. Consequently, CBT may be interpreted as a form of pseudo-community development driven by economic considerations and neo-liberal ideologies, rather than by principles of empowerment and social justice.

Waterfalls and Its Importance as a Tourist Attraction

Waterfalls have long been admired by poets and authors but scientists and academic scholars have only recently begun to give them some consideration (Eneyo *et al.*, 2022). Public interest in waterfalls is expanding, as seen by the abundance of books, how-to manuals, and travel websites written for "waterfall lovers" who go "waterfalling". In tourist literature, waterfalls may also be rated aesthetically based on their surroundings, height, and forms including plunge, horsetail, and cascade. Waterfall locations may draw visitors for a variety of reasons, including their sanctity, scenic appeal, or recreational value. For the joy of visiting a well-known destination they have heard about or seen marketed, visitors may also choose to visit some waterfalls. While choosing a location, tourists frequently have other pleasures in mind as well.

Nigeria is blessed with a wealth of beautiful, natural getaways, including waterfalls. It is a top tourist site for activities including parties, picnics, picture shoots, film shoots, academic study, business meetings, and

adventures among others. It is of significant ecological significance because, in addition to serving as barriers to the passage of creatures, they also provide specialised habitats that are important for conservation (Ajayi, 2020). There are many different types of waterfalls, including those with overhangs, steps, plunge pools, broad accurate shapes (like Horseshoe Falls), and long, narrow waterfalls. According to (Fennell & Cooper, 2020), following categories are used to classify waterfalls:

- **Cascade:** These include Dip Falls in Tasmania, Australia, and Minaret Falls in the Eastern Sierra of California.
- **Block Waterfall:** Shifen Waterfall in Taiwan and Skogafoss in Iceland are two examples of these waterfalls.
- **Chute:** Examples of these waterfalls include Barnafoss in Iceland and Murchison Falls in Uganda.
- **Cataract:** Thundering waves of the Iguazu River on the border between Brazil and Argentina are among the widest and wildest of cataracts.
- **Horsetail Waterfalls:** Nevada Falls in Yosemite National Park in California and Sanddalsfossen in Norway are examples of waterfalls that fall under this category.
- **Fan Waterfalls:** Fantail Falls in New Zealand and Friaren in Norway's Geiranger Fjord are two examples of these.
- **Plunge Waterfalls:** Rainbow Falls on the Big Island of Hawaii, Bridal Veil Falls near Raglan, New Zealand, and Mangawehero Falls near Waitomo, New Zealand are all examples of plunge waterfalls.
- **Multi-step Waterfalls:** Olumirin Waterfall in Erin-Ijesa is an example of this.
- **Segmented Waterfalls:** These waterfalls include the Seven Sisters in Norway's Geiranger Fjord and Dinner Falls in Queensland, Australia.
- **Punchbowl:** Punch Bowl Falls in Oregon and Tawhai Falls in Tongariro National Park in New Zealand are two examples.

The following are some of Nigeria's most beautiful waterfalls (Ogunojente *et al.*, (2021)):

1. **Matsirga Waterfall:** The Matsirga Waterfall is located in Kafanchan, Kaduna State, in the northern part of Nigeria. The cascade gets its water from springs atop the Kagoro hills and cascades from the cliffs to a pool approximately 25 meters below, where it empties into the surrounding hills. The waterfall is a collection of four separate waterfalls that cascade down in a gorgeous form that continues to captivate all visitors.
2. **Kwa Waterfall:** The Kwa Waterfall, which can be found in the Cross River National Park not far from Calabar, the state's capital, gets its water from the Kwa River. This waterfall is a treat to visitors who want to explore it at any time of the year due to its tropical location amidst the rain forest and vegetative park.
3. **The Obudu Waterfall:** The Obudu Waterfall, located on the Obudu Mountain near the Obudu Cattle Ranch resort in the eastern part of Nigeria, is not as big or large as the other waterfalls in the country but it still makes for an interesting sight. Wild animals including gorillas, monkeys, and uncommon birds frequently stop by this waterfall for a drink because it is a natural resort.
4. **Assop Waterfall:** In Plateau State, 64 kilometers separate the Assop Waterfall from Jos, the state's capital. One of the best natural attractions for tourists and thrill-seekers in the northern-central region of Nigeria. This waterfall is located along the Jos-Abuja Road. During holiday seasons, the Assop Waterfall is ideal for picnics, birdwatching, sightseeing, swimming, and other social activities.
5. **Agbokim Waterfall:** The Agbokim Waterfall in Cross River State is located nearly 315 kilometers to Calabar. The closest community in Etung LGA, Ikom, is around 17 kilometers away. It is also extremely close to the Nigeria-Cameroon border. Visitors from surrounding states frequently choose to visit the waterfall because of its appealing and entrancing tranquility, and many of them have been fortunate enough to see a rainbow traverse its aura at particular periods of the year.

6. **Owu Waterfall:** The Owu Waterfall is located in the Ifelodun Local Government Area of Kwara State, Nigeria. It is one of the loveliest waterfalls to visit in the south-western region of Nigeria. The cascade is famous for its nearly 330-foot waterfall that falls onto a rugged backdrop of hills and lush flora that attracts visitors. The flowing spray of water is refreshing and might be a great spot to take a bath.
7. **Gurara Waterfall:** The Gurara Waterfall is about 3 kilometers off the Minna-Suleja route and 30 minutes' drive from Abuja, the capital of the country. During the wet season, this waterfall pours down a drop of 30 metres and has a width of roughly 200 metres. After all rainfalls stop during the dry season, the waterfall loses its strength. The famous river Niger's intake, the Gurara River, appears to branch off into the cascade. This waterfall is ideal for educational study, photo and video shoots, bird watching, and other activities including group picnics.
8. **Awhum Waterfall:** The Awhum Waterfall is located in the eastern region of Nigeria, along the Enugu-9th Mile route, about 30 minutes' drive from Enugu State. A local Catholic monastery guards this spot to prevent vandals from destroying its beauty. This waterfall is fed by an unbroken river stream that cascades from a jagged cliff and passes through a stunning woodland. The best area in Enugu to go for both social and tourist attractions is this one.
9. **Farin Ruwa Waterfall:** The Bokkos LGA in Plateau State and the Wamba LGA in Nigeria's Nassarawa State share a boundary where the Farin Ruwa Waterfall is located. In Hausa, the word for "white waters" is Farin Ruwa. Some table-water firms come to this location to obtain water to bottle for marketing purposes. This waterfall, which cascades from a 150-metre-high rock, embodies the lovely majesty of the region's natural beauty and amazes all visitors. The region is ideal for climbing and study, among other social endeavours due to its volcanic rocks and granite topography.
10. **Erin-Ijesha Waterfall:** Olumirin Waterfall, which translates to "another deity," is another name for the Erin-Ijesha Waterfall. In the south-western region of Nigeria, in the town of Erin-Ijesha, lies this waterfall. This waterfall is located inside the community axes of Erin-Oke, Erin-Ijesha, and Erinmo along the Efon Ridge along the Ilesha-Akure motorway. The amazing feature of this waterfall is that it is a conglomeration of seven separate waterfalls that tumble down from the rock's upper cliffs and into a river pool that empties into a canopy of lush greenery.

The Erin-Ijesha waterfall has more beautiful features than others. Its uniqueness is solely attributable to the physical setting, which includes the seven various layers of rocks from which the water pours onto the flowing shape of the fall. The waterfall is in fact nature at its best in its entirety. Geographically, the waterfall is located in an area of Erin-Ijesha town in Osun State that was founded in 1140 AD and is heavily forested.

Stakeholders and their Roles in the Development and Management of Waterfall Attractions

The activities of stakeholders have a significant impact on the success or failure of tourism destinations, hence managers of tourism destination sites must be interested in stakeholder management while simultaneously guaranteeing sustainable competitive advantage. The community/residents, the government, the workforce, tourists or visitors, and the tourism industry are considered to be the primary stakeholders who play roles in the growth of tourism. Each of these parties is essential to the accomplishment of tourism-related operations (Hudson, 2006). These parties have significant roles to play in the growth and management of waterfall tourism, including:

Community or Residents: Local communities living around waterfalls are vital stakeholders in their development and management. They are quite knowledgeable about the local history, culture, and customs. Decision-making, maintaining cultural authenticity, and guaranteeing equitable sharing of tourism gains all depend heavily on their input. Local communities may participate directly in tourism-related activities by providing lodging, providing tour guides, or selling local goods. In order to ensure independence and raise the standards of life of the locals, tourism literature emphasises the value of grassroots community engagement (Hoogendoorn & Fitchet, 2018). Tourism has emerged as a viable option for socio-economic development, particularly in poor nations, under the aegis of the alternative

development paradigm if it incorporates sincere community participation. Numerous case studies from around the world show that tourism, if properly planned and developed through a thorough and real community participation, may greatly improve people' livelihoods and contribute to the socio-cultural and ecological protection.

Hennink and Bonnie (2022) affirm that the community is in charge of safeguarding and conserving waterfall locations. They take an active role in preserving the natural world, including the waterfall and the ecosystems that surround it. To keep the destination's beauty and integrity, this calls for actions such as waste management, pollution prevention, and the enforcement of laws. Infrastructure construction around waterfall destinations may involve locals. To construct access roads, walkways, bridges, viewing platforms, and security features (such as fences or guardrails), they could collaborate with authorities or organisations. They ensure that these infrastructures are well-maintained and safe for visitors.

The development of sustainable tourist practices near waterfall locations is the responsibility of the local community. To manage tourism-related tasks like planning guided tours, offering lodging, and promoting nearby establishments like restaurants or gift shops, they may find cooperatives or organisations. They make an effort to find a balance between luring tourists and protecting the region's natural and cultural heritage. For the local population, seeing waterfalls is frequently an important cultural experience (Asada and Yong, 2019). They might associate these natural wonders with customary beliefs, rites, or tales. In order to preserve and present its cultural legacy to visitors, the community is essential. To inform guests about their customs, history, and traditions, they might host cultural events, traditional performances, or interpretive facilities.

When tourists travel to waterfall destinations, the locals may help to inform them of the value of sustainable practices. They provide knowledge about the native flora and fauna, water conservation, garbage disposal, and ethical tourism. Additionally, they promote awareness of any ecological or cultural vulnerabilities that require protection. They might profit from the business prospects brought about by the development and administration of waterfall tourist spots. For the local community, tourism creates revenue and jobs, opening doors for business and means of subsistence (Alikor, 2022). The neighborhood may also make investments to diversify the local economy by fostering other industries like farming, handicrafts, or eco-friendly businesses. In general, the community's participation and active engagement are crucial to the development and administration of waterfall destinations in a sustainable manner. Their care guarantees that natural resources, cultural history, and financial advantages are preserved for upcoming generations.

Government and Regulatory Agencies: Key participants in the waterfall tourist industry include governmental entities at the local, state, and federal levels. They are in charge of establishing the rules, laws, and policies that will govern the growth and administration of the tourism industry. They keep an eye on licenses, permits, and adherence to safety and environmental regulations. Governments also subsidize the growth of tourism and provide infrastructure and public services. For the administration and development of waterfall tourism attractions, the government establishes the broad policy framework and recommendations. To ensure the sustainable use and conservation of these natural resources, this includes creating rules, legislation, and standards. They could set rules for visiting limits, security precautions, environmental protection, and cultural preservation. They are in charge of strategic planning and infrastructure development at waterfall locations. This can include the construction or improvement of visitor centers, viewing platforms, trails, interpretation facilities, and parking areas. They may also oversee the maintenance and upgrading of infrastructure to enhance visitor experiences and ensure accessibility (Ajulo *et al.*, 2017).

The government is essential in preserving the ecosystem around waterfall vacation spots. They create and uphold laws to safeguard the environment, wildlife, flora, and fauna. This can entail keeping an eye on and controlling practices that might damage the ecosystem, putting policies in place to stop pollution or deterioration, and working with relevant organisations to guarantee the long-term preservation of natural resources.

Visitors and Tourists: Visitors and tourists are participants in the waterfall tourism industry. Their actions, tastes, and feedback affect how tourism-related activities are created and run. Sustainable tourism

development depends on knowing what visitors want, encouraging responsible behaviour, and meeting their requirements (Ajayi, 2020).

Employees: Employees are accountable for providing excellent guest services and making sure visitors have a good time. They might provide information, advice, and recommendations to guests about the waterfall, nearby attractions, and amenities. This may entail giving out maps and pamphlets and responding to inquiries about accessibility, safety, and local laws. When it comes to safeguarding the natural surroundings of waterfall tourist sites, employees are essential. They might keep an eye on the behaviours of visitors, enact laws, and instruct visitors on how to protect the ecology (Babafemi *et al.*, 2021). This may entail controlling trash disposal, stopping contamination and keeping the area around the site clean responsible tourism.

Methodology

This study adopted a quantitative approach using a descriptive quantitative survey. The population for this study is all the residents in the Erin-Ijesha and Ipole Iloro communities in Osun and Ekiti States, respectively. This was estimated to be 3,777 (1837 from Erin-Ijesha and 1,940 from Ipole Iloro) people living in the two communities of the Erin-Ijesha Waterfall. Thus, the population size for this study is 3,777 residents. The sample size for a population size of 3,777 is 377, according to sample size educational research basics calculator table, a population size of 3,777 requires 377 respondents at a margin error of 5 per cent and confidence level of 95 per cent. The respondents were selected using non-probability sample, convenient or accidental sampling technique.

Results and Discussion of Findings

Percentage and charts were used to present the distribution of respondents by demographic factors. These are illustrated as follows:

Table/Figure 1: Distribution of Respondents by Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage %
Male	157	43.0
Female	208	57.0
Total	365	100.0

Source: Authors' Field Survey, 2024

Table/Figure 1 shows that of the 365 of the respondents, 157 (43.0%) were males while 208 (57.0%) were female. This indicates that female residents were more represented in this study than the male counterparts.

Table 2: Mean Ranking of Respondents' Responses on the Roles of Community in the Development of Waterfall Attractions in Southwest, Nigeria

N	As a resident of this community, my role in the development of the waterfall include:	Mean	SD	Rank
1	Involvement in waterfall-related policies making	3.60	.710	10 th
2	Ensuring the community needs are incorporated into the development decisions	3.53	.677	14 th
3	Giving government valuable feedback on different development projects	3.44	.695	19 th
4	Supplying labour to the attraction	3.58	.669	11 th

5	Involvement in economic activities (such as a petty trading) at the destination	3.54	.685	13 th
6	Supporting government conservation programmes (scientific research, monitoring and implementation of sustainable practices)	3.45	.696	16 th
7	Cooperating with business entrepreneurs and local leadership	3.45	.704	16 th
8	Supplying information and technical support to the attraction developers	3.45	.785	16 th
9	Creating awareness for the destination	3.26	.987	20 th
10	Serving as volunteers for developmental activities associated with waterfall	3.65	.950	6 th
11	Being part of waterfall project planning and implementation	3.81	.787	1 st
12	Consulting government to set up tourism plans and projects	3.79	.806	2 nd
13	Promoting tourist attractions that form the basis of waterfall development	3.77	.843	3 rd
14	Providing the major services at the destination such as accommodation, catering, transport and other services	3.75	.854	4 th
15	Determining how the waterfall is to be used in their community	3.66	.895	5 th
16	Constituting local residents to make decisions on waterfall development	3.63	1.013	8 th
17	Advertising and recommending the destination to others	3.58	1.121	12 th
18	Engaging in environmental preservation programs (waste recycling, tree planting, healthy product consumption etc.)	3.62	.914	9 th
19	organising cultural activities (religious festivities, parades, concerts, etc.) at the waterfall	3.52	1.081	15 th
20	Helping at the construction site of waterfall infrastructure (hotels, houses, roads, etc.)	3.65	1.001	6 th

Source: Authors' Field Survey, 2024

Table 2 shows the mean ranking of respondents' responses on the community's role on waterfall attractions development. The table shows that all of the items have mean scores that are above the average (benchmark) mean value of 3.00 for determining the roles of the community with respect to the view of the respondents. This implies that the respondents agreed that all the listed items constitute the roles of the community in the development of waterfall attractions. However, items 11 (with mean and standard deviation values of 3.81 and .787), 12 (with mean and standard deviation values of 3.79 and .806) and 13 (with mean and standard deviation values of 3.77 and .843) were the topmost ranked items (1st, 2nd and 3rd respectively). The inference drawn from this result is that there are numerous roles that the community need to play in the development of waterfall attractions in Southwest Nigeria and some of which are being part of waterfall project planning and implementation and consulting government to set up tourism plans and projects

Discussion of Findings

As indicated by the findings of this work, there are numerous roles that the community need to play in the development of waterfall attractions in Southwest, Nigeria; some of which are being part of waterfall project planning and implementation, consulting government to set up tourism plans and projects and promotion of tourist attractions. The findings stress that, in Southwest Nigeria, the development of waterfall attractions involves active participation from local communities in various roles essential for planning, implementation and promotion. To buttress this, Eneyo (2022) submits that the community-based tourism theory emphasises the importance of involving local communities in tourism development to ensure equitable benefits, preserve cultural heritage and minimise environmental impact.

Equally, the study reveals that the local communities in Southwest Nigeria could play crucial roles in planning and implementing waterfall projects by contributing local knowledge, resources and labour.

Falade-Obalade and Suchi (2014) add that they could collaborate with government authorities to develop tourism plans that benefit both residents and visitors, advocating sustainable practices and inclusive development. Furthermore, communities actively promote tourist attractions through various channels to attract visitors, generate income and raise awareness about sustainable tourism practices.

Previous empirical studies have highlighted the positive impacts of community involvement in waterfall development, such as increased community empowerment, improved livelihoods and enhanced visitor experiences. However, challenges such as power imbalances, resource constraints and conflicting interests among stakeholders have also been identified in some studies. Supporting previous research findings which include the belief that community participation leads to more sustainable and authentic tourism experiences, enhances the quality of tourism services and fosters a sense of ownership among community members. Conversely, Ajayi (2020) stresses that challenges such as power dynamics, limited resources and conflicting priorities may hinder the full engagement of communities in tourism development. Hence, as established by this study, the active involvement of local communities in the development of waterfall attractions in Southwest Nigeria is crucial for promoting responsible tourism practices, enhancing visitor experiences and ensuring the long-term sustainability of tourist destinations. By aligning with community-based tourism principles and drawing on insights from previous studies, stakeholders can leverage the knowledge and resources of communities to create thriving and resilient tourism destinations.

Community participation in the development of waterfall attractions in Southwest Nigeria is considered low. This finding has shown a notable poor participation by local residents or communities in the development of waterfall attractions in Southwest Nigeria. This poor participation poses challenges for sustainable waterfall tourism growth and community well-being. Through the perspective of community-based tourism theory, which stresses the importance of engaging local communities in tourism initiatives to ensure fair benefits, preserve cultural authenticity and minimise environmental impact, this issue can be better understood. Comparing these findings with past empirical studies, a pattern where active community participation in waterfall development has led to positive outcomes such as enhanced community empowerment, improved livelihoods and enriched visitor experiences has been observed. However, challenges such as power dynamics, limited resources and conflicting interests among stakeholders have also been noted in previous research. Reasons for prioritising community participation include the risk of tourism projects not aligning with local needs without community input, the potential for fostering a sense of ownership and pride in local initiatives and the valuable local knowledge that residents can contribute to enhance the authenticity of visitor experiences. These findings emphasise the critical need to encourage meaningful community participation in the planning and execution of waterfall tourism projects in Southwest Nigeria. By embracing principles of community-based tourism and working to overcome barriers to participation, stakeholders can create tourism initiatives that are more sustainable, inclusive and beneficial for both local residents and visitors' promotion of tourist attractions.

Conclusion

The communities have numerous roles to play in the development of waterfall attractions in Southwest, Nigeria. However, their participation level in these developmental tasks is low, with which many of them were very dissatisfied. Despite this, they still believed that the presence of the waterfall attractions has improved their cultural heritage and environmental sustainability. Furthermore, while the residents were similar on the basis of gender in regards to their levels of participation in waterfall attractions development, satisfaction with such participation and impact of the development on the host community, they differed on the basis of age and religion.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it was recommended that:

1. The government and the community leaders should implement community engagement programmes to raise awareness about the importance of community involvement in the development of waterfall attractions. This can help in increasing people's level of participation.

2. Public and private tourism stakeholders should, on a regular basis, organise workshops and training sessions to build the skills and knowledge of community members regarding sustainable tourism practices and development of waterfall attractions.
3. Tourism stakeholders should involve community members in the decision-making process related to the development of waterfall attractions to ensure their voices are heard and their needs are considered.
4. Government and other concerned tourism promoters should establish feedback mechanisms to gather input from the community about their levels of satisfaction and areas for improvement in the development process.
5. Government and private organisations should develop initiatives that focus on preserving the cultural heritage of the community while developing the waterfall attractions to ensure that local traditions and practices are respected and promoted.
6. Tourism stakeholders should conduct environmental education programmes to raise awareness about the importance of environmental sustainability in the development of tourism attractions and encourage community members to actively participate in conservation efforts.
7. The government and private tourism investors should design programmes that bridge the generational gap and involve community members of all ages in the development of waterfall attractions to promote inclusivity and diversity.
8. Developers of waterfall attractions should take into consideration the religious beliefs and practices of the community members when planning and implementing development projects to ensure that they are culturally sensitive and respectful.
9. Government should encourage a sense of ownership among community members by involving them in various aspects of the development process, such as planning, implementation and maintenance of the waterfall attractions.
10. Government and tourism investors should partner with local religious and community leaders to facilitate communication, address concerns and mobilise community members

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